

Transition towards environment friendly consumer products by co-creation of an oxidoreductase foundry

GA no 101000607

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Start date: 1st June 2021. End date: 31st May 2025

Public Executive Summary of deliverable

D5.3: Oxidase-based pilot system for biobleaching

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000607

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Executive summary log

Submission	29/04/2025
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Main achievements/outcomes

One of the main objectives of the OXIPRO project is based on the development of a sustainable and circular biobleaching process for cotton textiles. This process is structured in two main stages: i) Step 1, dedicated to the production of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) from carbohydrate-rich wastewaters, using oxidases, and ii) Step 2, which uses the generated H_2O_2 for cotton bleaching with the help of an activator agent.

An exhaustive characterization of two carbohydrate oxidases was performed: the N-acetylglucosamine oxidase (NagOX) and the cellobiose oxidase (COX). Both enzymes were evaluated using wastewater from the cotton pre-washing stage as substrate. The results obtained indicate that both oxidases are suitable for carrying out hydrogen peroxide production in Step 1. However, it was determined that their optimal application requires different strategies.

The cellobiose oxidase (COX) showed broad specificity towards substrates present in the wastewater, which facilitates its direct application in the effluent.

On the other hand, the N-acetylglucosamine oxidase (NagOX), given its substrate specificity, requires a preliminary enzymatic treatment step of the wastewater using other enzymes, such as glucoamylases, to release the carbohydrates that can be processed by the oxidase.

The impact of pH control on enzymatic performance was studied. While the implementation of a pH control system did not have a significant effect on the performance of COX, it was observed that NagOX experienced a significant improvement in its performance when such control was applied.

Furthermore, the high variability in the parameters of the pre-wash wastewater between different batches was confirmed, leading to noticeable fluctuations in the final amount of H₂O₂ produced by both enzymes. COX appeared to show more robust behavior and consistency against these variations in the wastewater composition.

Despite the challenges presented by wastewater variability, the application of both COX and NagOX was successful in producing relevant amounts of hydrogen peroxide.

Regarding Step 2, optimization studies of the biobleaching process were carried out using an H₂O₂ activator. Due to the complexity and variability of real wastewater, synthetic wastewater mimicking the characteristics of real wastewater was used for this phase. The optimal condition led to a whiteness index just a 14% less than the target.

The reported work has been conducted by **UAB** in collaboration by the four partners **NOVO, RUG, VTT** and **ZORLU**.